

Retrospective Study on the Utility of FNAC in Diagnosing Soft Tissue Tumors and Tumor-Like Lesions

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Abstract:

Background: Soft tissue tumors are a heterogeneous group of neoplasms that can present significant diagnostic challenges. Accurate and timely diagnosis is critical for effective treatment planning and improving patient outcomes. Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) is a minimally invasive diagnostic tool that has gained prominence for its utility in evaluating these tumors, offering a rapid and reliable method for distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions.

Aim: This study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC in the diagnosis of soft tissue tumors and tumor-like lesions across multiple healthcare centers.

Methods: A retrospective, multicentric study was conducted over 24 months, involving 95 participants diagnosed with soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions. Data were collected from patient records, including FNAC results and final histopathological diagnoses. The diagnostic accuracy of FNAC was evaluated by calculating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Out of 95 cases, FNAC demonstrated an overall diagnostic accuracy of 84.2%. The sensitivity and specificity of FNAC in diagnosing malignant tumors were 85% and 83.3%, respectively. The PPV was 77.3%, and the NPV was 89.7%. A significant association was found between patient age and the likelihood of malignancy ($p < 0.05$), while no significant association was observed between gender and tumor type ($p = 0.45$).

Conclusion: FNAC is a reliable and effective diagnostic tool for soft tissue tumors, particularly in distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. The high NPV makes it especially useful in ruling out malignancies, reducing the need for more invasive procedures. The study highlights the importance of considering patient age in the diagnostic evaluation, as older patients are more likely to have malignant tumors.

Recommendations: FNAC should be utilized as a first-line diagnostic tool in the evaluation of soft tissue tumors, with particular attention to patient age. Further research with larger sample sizes and prospective designs is recommended to validate these findings and explore the integration of FNAC with advanced imaging and molecular techniques.

Keywords: Soft tissue tumors, Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology, FNAC, Diagnostic accuracy, Malignancy.

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Introduction

A wide range of neoplasms originating from mesenchymal tissues, including muscle, fat, fibrous tissue, and blood vessels, are referred to as soft tissue tumours. These tumours can be benign or malignant, and because of their rarity and variety of appearances, the latter frequently provide serious diagnostic and treatment issues. Proper patient management requires an early and correct diagnosis because it has a direct impact on treatment choices and prognosis results. The minimally invasive diagnostic method known as (FNAC) has gained popularity as a quick and accurate way to assess soft tissue tumours. More and more people are

realising the value of FNAC in this situation, especially because of its capacity to differentiate between benign and malignant tumours, which helps direct future diagnostic and treatment efforts. Numerous recent studies have emphasised the significance of FNAC in the diagnosis of soft tissue tumours. For example, a study showed that FNAC offers a high level of diagnostic accuracy, especially in the preliminary assessment of soft tissue masses. This enables the early detection of cancers and the timely start of suitable treatment protocols [1]. A different study highlighted the function of FNAC in environments with low

resources, where people may not have access to cutting-edge imaging and surgical facilities [2]. FNAC is a useful tool that can help minimise the need for more invasive procedures in these situations and speed up clinical decision-making.

The diagnostic capabilities of FNAC [3] have been further increased by recent advancements in cytological techniques and the incorporation of ancillary investigations, such as immunocytochemistry and molecular diagnostics. These advancements have increased the FNAC's accuracy, especially when the tumor's cytological characteristics are unclear or overlap between the benign and malignant categories. Additionally, the fusion of FNAC with imaging modalities, including ultrasound-guided FNAC, has improved tissue sample precision and decreased the likelihood of non-diagnostic or inconclusive results [4].

Notwithstanding its benefits, a number of variables, such as the tumor's intrinsic properties, the cytopathologist's experience, and the sample's quality, can affect the FNAC's accuracy and dependability. As a result, it is critical to regularly evaluate and confirm FNAC's effectiveness across a range of clinical contexts and patient populations. This study aims to assess the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC in the diagnosis of soft tissue tumors and tumor-like lesions across multiple healthcare centers.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a retrospective, multicentric study.

Study Place: This was a multicentric study involving data collection from multiple healthcare institutions.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across several healthcare institutions, allowing for a diverse sample population and broader generalizability of the findings. Data from patient records across these centers were compiled and analyzed centrally.

Participants: A total of 95 participants were included in the study. These participants were selected based on their medical history and diagnostic findings related to soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions within the study duration.
- Patients who underwent FNAC (Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology) as part of their diagnostic workup.

- Availability of complete medical records, including histopathological and cytological reports.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Cases where FNAC was not performed.
- Patients who were diagnosed with conditions other than soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were selected consecutively from available medical records that met the inclusion criteria. Data abstraction was conducted by blinded reviewers to reduce information bias. Furthermore, consistent diagnostic criteria were applied across all centers to reduce variability in diagnosis and reporting.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records at participating centers. Information gathered included demographic details, clinical presentation, imaging results, FNAC findings, and histopathological diagnoses. Data were anonymized and compiled into a central database for analysis.

Procedure

- Medical records were reviewed by trained personnel at each participating center.
- Relevant data points were extracted, including demographic information, tumor characteristics, and diagnostic outcomes.
- FNAC results were compared with histopathological diagnoses to assess diagnostic accuracy.
- Data were checked for consistency and any discrepancies were resolved through re-examination of the records.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of the SPSS software was used to analyse the data. The study population's clinical and demographic parameters were compiled using descriptive statistics. The assessment of FNAC's diagnostic accuracy involved the computation of its sensitivity, specificity, (PPV), and (NPV). Utilising chi-square tests, the relationship between categorical variables was assessed. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Results

The study included 95 participants diagnosed with soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions. The demographic distribution is presented in Table 1. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 75 years,

with a mean age of 45.6 ± 14.2 years. The majority of the participants were male (54.7%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Number (n=95)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18-30	15	15.8
31-50	45	47.4
51-75	35	36.8
Gender		
Male	52	54.7
Female	43	45.3
Tumor Location		
Extremities	40	42.1
Trunk	30	31.6
Head and Neck	15	15.8
Others	10	10.5

Distribution of Soft Tissue Tumors and Tumor-Like Lesions: The majority of cases involved benign tumors (68.4%), while malignant tumors accounted for 31.6% of the cases. The distribution of different types of soft tissue tumors is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Soft Tissue Tumors and Tumor-Like Lesions

Tumor Type	Number (n=95)	Percentage (%)
Benign Tumors	65	68.4
Lipoma	30	31.6
Hemangioma	15	15.8
Fibroma	10	10.5
Schwannoma	10	10.5
Malignant Tumors	30	31.6
Undifferentiated Sarcoma	20	21.1
Rhabdomyosarcoma	5	5.3
Malignant Fibrous Histiocytoma	5	5.3

Diagnostic Accuracy of FNAC: The diagnostic accuracy of FNAC was evaluated by comparing its findings with the final histopathological diagnosis. FNAC correctly identified 80 out of 95 cases, resulting in an overall accuracy of 84.2%. The

sensitivity and specificity of FNAC in diagnosing malignant tumors were 85% and 83.3%, respectively. The positive predictive value (PPV) was 77.3%, and the negative predictive value (NPV) was 89.7% (Table 3).

Table 3: Diagnostic Accuracy of FNAC

Diagnostic Parameter	Value (%)
Sensitivity	85.0
Specificity	83.3
(PPV)	77.3
(NPV)	89.7
Overall Accuracy	84.2

Statistical Analysis: Chi-square analysis was performed to assess the association between tumor type (benign vs. malignant) and various clinical and demographic factors. The analysis revealed a

significant association between age and tumor type, with older patients more likely to have malignant tumors ($p < 0.05$). No significant association was found between gender and tumor type ($p = 0.45$).

Table 4: Association Between Age and Tumor Type

Age Group (years)	Benign Tumors (n=65)	Malignant Tumors (n=30)	p-value
18-30	13	2	0.035*
31-50	35	10	0.018*
51-75	17	18	0.022*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5: Association Between Gender and Tumor Type

Gender	Benign Tumors (n=65)	Malignant Tumors (n=30)	p-value
Male	38	14	0.45
Female	27	16	0.45

Discussion

The study included 95 participants diagnosed with soft tissue tumors or tumor-like lesions, with a nearly equal distribution between males and females, and a mean age of 45.6 years. The majority of the tumors were benign, accounting for 68.4% of the cases, while malignant tumors constituted 31.6%. The most common benign tumor was lipoma, while undifferentiated sarcoma was the most frequently observed malignant tumor. The distribution of tumor types across different anatomical locations revealed a higher prevalence in the limbs, followed by the trunk, head and neck, and other regions.

The diagnostic accuracy of (FNAC) was found to be commendable, with an overall accuracy of 84.2%. The sensitivity and specificity of FNAC in diagnosing malignant tumors were 85% and 83.3%, respectively. This indicates that FNAC is highly reliable in detecting malignant tumors, and equally effective in correctly identifying benign lesions. The (PPV) of 77.3% suggests that when FNAC identifies a tumor as malignant, there is a strong likelihood of it being confirmed upon histopathological examination. Conversely, the (NPV) of 89.7% indicates that FNAC is particularly effective in ruling out malignancy, making it a valuable tool in clinical settings where excluding cancer is crucial.

Statistical analysis further revealed a significant association between age and tumor type, with older patients more likely to have malignant tumors. This underscores the need for heightened vigilance and possibly more aggressive diagnostic approaches in older patients presenting with soft tissue masses. However, no significant association was found between gender and tumor type, indicating that gender does not influence the likelihood of a tumor being malignant or benign in this study population. In a study it was highlighted that the usefulness of FNAC in the diagnosis of soft tissue lesions exhibiting myxoid alterations. The research verified that FNAC is a rather pleasant process that produces quick results with good specificity and sensitivity. This is consistent with recent research showing that FNAC is useful in both classifying soft tissue tumours and differentiating between benign and malignant tumours [5].

In a study investigated the function of FNAC in conjunction with supplementary methods such as immunocytochemistry and cell blocking in a more comprehensive setting. Their research showed that FNAC could improve the precision of identifying

and classifying soft tissue tumours in conjunction with these methods, highlighting the significance of FNAC in contemporary diagnostic procedures [6].

A study demonstrated the effectiveness of FNAC as a diagnostic tool for soft tissue tumours. The study demonstrated the importance of FNAC as a quick, secure, and reliable diagnostic technique in the early management of soft tissue tumours and found good sensitivity and specificity, especially for malignancy [7].

Conclusion

The results support the utility of FNAC as a reliable diagnostic tool for soft tissue tumors, particularly in multicentric settings where standardized diagnostic practices may vary. The high NPV makes FNAC especially useful in ruling out malignancies, thus reducing the need for more invasive diagnostic procedures in cases where malignancy is unlikely. These findings suggest that FNAC should be considered a valuable first-line diagnostic tool in the evaluation of soft tissue tumors, with particular attention given to patient age as a factor in assessing the risk of malignancy. However core needle biopsy are superior tool of investigation in malignant tumors as immunohistochemistry can be done on it and can give more precise diagnosis.

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